

SHORT NOTES

Spectrophotometric Investigation of the Binding of Nickel to Transfusion Gelatin

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In spite of the great importance of nickel in many biochemical processes involving trypsin¹, arginase², and alkaline phosphatase,³ its interaction with protein, unlike those of copper, calcium, iron etc., has received very limited attention so far. Nyilasi⁴, Plekhan⁵, Kato⁶, and their co-workers, however, pointed out that nickel ion did enter into combination with proteins including gelatin under the condition of biuret reaction and that the metal ion was mainly linked⁷ to enolised peptide groups.

As physico-chemical studies on nickel ion binding to more complex proteins, such as, gelatin and casein, under conditions other than that of biuret reaction are lacking in the literature, spectrophotometric investigation on the combination of nickel with more characterised collagen types of proteins, such as transfusion gelatin⁷, has been undertaken⁸⁻¹¹.

Transfusion gelatin (conc. 6%, M.W. 75000), supplied by the Director, National Chemical Laboratory, Poona, was used in this investigation.

Chemically pure sample of nickel chloride was employed for the preparation of its stock solution in double distilled (all-glass) water and its strength was determined gravimetrically¹². Walpole acetate and the citrate buffers were prepared from 0.05M solutions of acetic acid, sodium acetate, citric acid, and NaOH¹³. The pH of different buffer solutions was measured with a Beckman pH-meter, Model H by using glass electrodes.

Light absorption measurements were carried out by a Beckman spectrophotometer, Model DU, using tungsten lamp as the light source (light path 1 mm) and corex cell of 1 cm depth at room temperature (25°).

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Procedure

(i) Following sets of solutions were arranged for light absorption measurements: Solutions of nickel chloride (4 mM) were taken with varying concentrations of transfusion gelatin, viz., 0, 0.15, 0.75, 0.90, 1.50, and 1.80% in 25-ml pyrex conical flasks and the total volume was made to 10 ml by adding a requisite amount of water and 2.5 ml of the acetate buffer (pH 5.0).

(ii) Similarly, at a fixed concentration of the protein (0.6%) 2,3,4,5, and 8mM solutions of nickel chloride were mixed with 2.5 ml of the acetate buffer of pH 5.0 (for pH 5.95 the citrate buffer was used) and the total volume was made to 10 ml.

(iii) At a given concentration of transfusion gelatin (0.6%) and that of nickel chloride ($4.0 \times 10^{-3}M$), 2.5 ml- portions of acetate buffers of different pH's (3.21, 4.01, 4.50 and 5.00) were added, keeping the total volume 10 ml.

TABLE I

A. Effect of protein concentration. (Conc. of $NiCl_2 = 4.0 \times 10^{-3}M$. pH=5.0).

Protein conc. (%)	..	0	0.15	0.60	0.75	0.90	1.50	1.80
λ_{max} (m μ)	..	750	675	650	650	650	625	625
Molar extinct. coeff. (ϵ)	..	3.0	8.5	10.0	11.0	12.0	14.5	15.0

B. Effect of metal-ion concentration. (Conc. of transfusion gelatin = 0.6%. pH = 5.0).

$NiCl_2$ ($\times 10^{-3}M$)	..	2	3	4	5	8
λ_{max} (m μ)	..	650	650	650	675	675
ϵ -values	..	17.0	12.0	10.0	9.2	7.5

C. Effect of pH. (Protein conc. = 0.6%. Conc. of $NiCl_2 = 4.0 \times 10^{-3}M$).

pH	..	5.95	5.00	4.50	4.01	3.21
λ_{max} (m μ)	..	600	650	675	675	725
ϵ -values	..	12.0	10.0	9.0	8.7	7.0

In the pH range 3.21-5.95, where the interaction of nickel and transfusion gelatin has been studied, all the 84 carboxyl groups of the protein would offer principal sites for metal binding since the pK value⁶ of the group under consideration is 4.7. On the basis of our present spectrophotometric studies, we could conclusively show that nickel did enter into combination with transfusion gelatin preferentially through its carboxyl groups.

From Table I, it is evident that a marked increase in the extinction coefficient of nickel (from 3.0 to 8.5) takes place when a small amount of the protein (0.15%) is introduced into the nickel-buffer mixture at pH 5.0. This behaviour can only be attributed to the uptake of metal ions by the protein. Absorption studies carried out at still higher protein concentrations showed further increase in the extinction coefficient values with increase in the concentration of transfusion gelatin (ϵ -values increased from 8.5 at 0.15% to 15.0 at 1.8%). Moreover, the position of the absorption maxima also shifted to a shorter wave length (675 m μ for 0.15% and 625 m μ for 1.8%), indicating dependence of the nickel-ion binding to transfusion gelatin on metal-protein ratio at a given pH, greater metal binding taking

place with decrease in this ratio. Furthermore, the shifts in spectroscopic peaks towards shorter wave lengths suggest that nitrogen atom of the protein does play a role in the nickel-gelatin interaction.

The spectrophotometric results, obtained with varying concentrations of the metal ion at a given pH (5.0) and the protein concentrations (0.6%), lend further support to the above contention (Table I). The absorption maxima, however, did not significantly change ($\lambda_{\max}$ 650-675 $m\mu$).

As the pH was increased from 3.21 to 5.95, ϵ -values increased from 7 to 12 (Table I). This is quite understandable in view of the fact that carboxyl groups (pK value 4.7) of the protein become successively deprotonated with increase in pH and make themselves available for combination with nickel. One of the striking features of these investigations is the unusual spectroscopic peak at pH 5.95 ($\lambda_{\max}$ 600 $m\mu$). This can only be ascribed to the fact that at this pH, the participation of the nitrogen atom becomes increasingly important. In the pH range 3.21-5.00, absorption measurements showed that nickel was bound primarily through the carboxyl groups of the protein. The position of absorption maxima in the vicinity of 700 $m\mu$, characteristic of predominantly nickel-carboxyl type of linkages⁴, further supports this view point.

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